

Technical Marvels, Part 5: Chess Automaton

Chess robots: from a fake automaton to a world champion program

For a long time, chess was considered the epitome of the human mind, a touchstone for artificial intelligence. Alan Turing had already dealt with this topic. In 1770, Wolfgang von Kempelen built the chess-playing Turk, in 1912 Leonardo Torres y Quevedo created an end-game machine, and in 1951 Norbert Wiener played against Torres y Quevedo's machine in Paris. In 1997, Garry Kasparov lost in New York to IBM's Deep Blue chess-playing computer.

The mechanical Turk, a fake automaton

In the 18th century, Wolfgang von Kempelen's victorious mechanical Turk (1770) amazed the world, see Figs.1-4. However, there was a person hidden inside. Charles Babbage is said to have lost a game against the fake automaton in 1819, similar to Napoleon.

Fig.1: Chess-playing Turk by Wolfgang von Kempelen (1783). Source: Karl Gottlieb von Windisch; Christian von Mechel: Karl Gottlieb von Windisch's Briefe über den Schachspieler des Hrn. von Kempelen nebst drey Kupferstichen, die diese berühmte Maschine vorstellen, Basel 1783

Fig.2: Chess-playing Turk by Wolfgang von Kempelen (1785). Source: Karl Gottlieb von Windisch; Christian von Mechel: Karl Gottlieb von Windisch's Briefe über den Schachspieler des Hrn. von Kempelen nebst drey Kupferstichen, die diese berühmte Maschine vorstellen, Basel 1783

Fig.3: Chess-playing Turk by Wolfgang von Kempelen (1789). Source: Joseph Friedrich Freyherr zu Racknitz,: Über den Schachspieler des Herrn von Kempelen und dessen Nachbildung, Joh. Gottl. Immanuel Breitkopf, Leipzig und Dresden 1789

Fig.4: Chess-playing Turk by Wolfgang von Kempelen (1789). Source: Joseph Friedrich Freyherr zu Racknitz: Über den Schachspieler des Herrn von Kempelen und dessen Nachbildung, Joh. Gottl. Immanuel Breitkopf, Leipzig und Dresden 1789

There is a functional replica of the mechanical Turk in the Heinz Nixdorf Museum Forum in Paderborn, see Fig.5.

Fig.5: Chess-playing Turk by Wolfgang von Kempelen (replica from 2004). Credit Sergei Magel/HNF

End-game machine by Torres y Quevedo

The Spanish engineer Leonardo Torres y Quevedo, who built a cable car over Niagara Falls, also created two chess-playing machines called El ajedrecista (chess player). The first, from 1912, was demonstrated in Paris in 1914. The machine plays with a king and rook (white) against a king (black). The second model was designed in 1920, see Fig.6. Both machines have survived and are located in Madrid.

Fig.6: El ajedrecista by Leonardo Torres y Quevedo, his second chess-playing machine. Credit Museo Leonardo Torres Quevedo, Escuela tecnica superior de ingenieros de caminos, canales y puertos. Universidad politecnica de Madrid.

At the Paris conference “Les machines à calculer et la pensée humaine“ in 1951, the U.S. cyberneticist Norbert Wiener played against the second version of this machine, see Fig.7.

Norbert Wiener playing the chess automaton (designed by Torres y Quevedo) at the 1951 Cybernetics Conference in Paris

Fig.7: Norbert Wiener and the chess-playing machine. In 1951, the U.S. cyberneticist Norbert Wiener (right) plays against Leonardo Torres y Quevedo's end-game machine at the Paris computer science conference. The device is supervised by his son (left). The machine (white, with king and rook) plays against the human (black, with king). Credit Studio Constantin, Paris.

First World Microcomputer Chess Championship in London in 1980

In 1980, the first World Microcomputer Chess Championship took place in London, see WMCCC 1980: https://www.chessprogramming.org/index.php?title=WMCCC_1980,

World Microcomputer Chess Championships:

https://www.chessprogramming.org/World_Microcomputer_Chess_Championship,

1st WMCCC London 1980: https://www.schach-computer.info/wiki/index.php?title=1._WMCCC_London_1980.

The organizer was the famous British international chess master David Levy. I took part with "Viktor", a program developed by the Privates Forschungsinstitut für Androidenteknik (Pfiat) in Darmstadt. I had examined the computer, named in honor of the long-time vice world champion Viktor Kortschnoi, on behalf of the Siemens-Nixdorf company. Thanks to a complex qualification, the program was admitted to the tournament. The Russian grandmaster Kortschoi was living in exile in Switzerland at the time. The championship was dramatic. Viktor beat the queen of the program that would later become world champion, but then collapsed, probably due to overheating. Re-entering the position took a lot of time, so that Viktor ended up in 10th place (out of 14), see Fig.8.

“The First World Microcomputer Chess Championship took place from September 04, 1980 to September 09, 1980, Cunard International Hotel, London, United Kingdom. This event is also known as the 3rd [PCW Microcomputer Chess Championship](#) or [Personal Computer World Exhibition](#), also the inofficial 1st [European Microcomputer Chess Championship](#). Being held under the auspices of the [ICCA](#) and [FIDE](#), multiple entries from same authors were possible. [Dan](#) and [Kathe Spracklen](#) had five [Sargon](#) versions running in various computers, [Chess Challenger](#), [Boris Experimental](#), [Sargon 2.0](#), [Sargon 2.5 Modular GS](#), and [Sargon 2.5 Auto RB](#), and were just affiliated with [Fidelity Electronics](#) and primary authors of the winning entity Chess Challenger. Remarkably, Chess Challenger won its last three round games versus three other Sargon programs, and was quite lucky as already in [round 2](#) versus [Viktor](#).” source: [WMCCC 1980 - Chessprogramming wiki](#)

Final Standing

[5]

#	Program	CC	1	2	3	4	5	P	SOS	SoDOS
1	Chess Challenger	US	12w1	10b1	2w1	7b1	5w1	5	13	13
2	Boris Experimental	US	14b1	8w1	1b0	3w1	7w1	4	13	8
3	Mike 3.0 ^[6]	GB	10w1	7b½	11w1	2b0	4b½	3	13½	6¼
4	Rook 4.0	SE	9w0	12b½	10b1	6b1	3w½	3	12	7¼
5	Sargon 2.0	US	11w0	9b1	13w1	12b1	1b0	3	12	5
6	Gambiet 80	NL	7w0	11b1	8w1	4w0	12b1	3	11½	6
7	Sargon 2.5 Modular GS	US	6b1	3w½	9b1	1w0	2b0	2½	17½	7
8	Sargon 2.5 Auto RB	US	13w1	2b0	6b0	11w1	9w½	2½	12½	4¼
9	Vega 1.7	GB	4b1	5w0	7w0	13w1	8b½	2½	12	5¼
10	Viktor	CH	3b0	1w0	4w0	14w1	13b1	2	12	1
11	Albatross	GB	5b1	6w0	3b0	8b0	14w1	2	11½	3
12	Fafner 2	GB	1b0	4w½	14b1	5w0	6w0	1½	14	1½
13	Princess	SE	8b0	14w1	5b0	9b0	10w0	1	10	0
14	Killer Chess IV	GB	2w0	13b0	12w0	10b0	11b0	0	10½	0

- [CC Country Codes](#)
- [SOS: Sum of Opponent Scores](#)
- [SoDOS: Sum of Defeated Opponent Scores](#)

Fig.8: 1980 World Microcomputer Chess Championship in London, results. Source: [WMCCC 1980 - Chessprogramming wiki](#)

Gold rush

At that time, there was a gold rush for chess-playing computers. Many manufacturers were hoping for high profits. I subsequently examined all of the 20 or more devices available on the market for Stiftung Warentest in Berlin. The large comparison test was published in the magazine “test” (volume 16, no. 8, August 1981, pages 22–29), see Fig.9 (overview) and Fig.10 (results, 1 of 6 pages).

Schachcomputer-Turnier		Punkte: 1 = gewonnen, 0 = verloren, 1/2 = remis																
		Runde 1			Runde 2			Runde 3			Runde 4			Runde 5			Punkte-stand	Platz
Nr.	Computer	Farbe	Gegner	Punkte	Farbe	Gegner	Punkte	Farbe	Gegner	Punkte	Farbe	Gegner	Punkte	Farbe	Gegner	Punkte		
1	Boris 2,5 ARB	W	10	1	S	17	1	W	11	1	W	3	0	S	13	1	4	2
2	Intelligent Chess	W	11	0	S	12	1	W	18	1	S	15	1/2	W	10	1	3 1/2	3/4
3	Morphy Encore	W	12	1	S	14	1	W	13	1	S	1	1	W	4	1	5	1
4	Mephisto	W	13	0	S	10	1	W	17	1	S	11	1	S	3	0	3	5-8
5	Commodore Chessmate	W	14	0	S	18	0	W	12	1	S	10	0	W	16	1	2	10-15
6	Chess Champion Super System III	W	15	1/2	S	13	0	W	16	1	S	18	1	W	17	0	2 1/2	9
7	Chess Challenger 7	W	16	1	S	11	0	W	15	1/2	S	17	0	W	14	0	1 1/2	16
8	Chess Champion Pocket Chess	W	17	0	S	16	1	W	10	0	S	14	1	W	15	0	2	10-15
9	Chess Challenger Grandmaster Voice	W	18	1	S	15	0	W	14	1	S	13	0	W	11	1	3	5-8
10	Chess Challenger 8 Sensory	S	1	0	W	4	0	S	8	1	W	5	1	S	2	0	2	10-15
11	Boris Diplomat	S	2	1	W	7	1	S	1	0	W	4	0	S	9	0	2	10-15
12	Chess Challenger Voice	S	3	0	W	2	0	S	5	0	W	16	1	W	18	1	2	10-15
13	Boris 2.5 MGS	S	4	1	W	6	1	S	3	0	W	9	1	W	1	0	3	5-8
14	Chess Champion Chess Partner 2000	S	5	1	W	3	0	S	9	0	W	8	0	S	7	1	2	10-15
15	Chess Challenger Sensory Voice	S	6	1/2	W	9	1	S	7	1/2	W	2	1/2	S	8	1	3 1/2	3/4
16	Conic Computer Chess	S	7	0	W	8	0	S	6	0	S	12	0	S	5	0	0	18
17	Chess Challenger 10	S	8	1	W	1	0	S	4	0	W	7	1	S	6	1	3	5-8
18	Chessmate WA 270	S	9	0	W	5	1	S	2	0	W	6	0	S	12	0	1	17

Fig.9: 1981 Comparison test, overview of the test results. Source: Stiftung Warentest (ed.): Test Schachcomputer. Fast alle mattgesetzt, in: test, volume 16, no. 8, August 1981, page 23

26 Test Schachcomputer: Einzelergebnisse

Fabrikat Anbieter-Adressen siehe Seite 25	Boris 2,5 ARB (Chafitz Sargon 2,5 ARB)	Mephisto	Boris Diplomat 80 ²⁾
Preis nach Markterhebung in DM	1998,- bis 2500,-	498,- bis 550,-	198,- bis 225,-
Mittlerer Preis in DM	2498,-	548,-	198,-

test-Qualitätsurteil	gut	zufriedenstellend	mangelhaft
TECHNISCHE MERKMALE Abmessungen des Grundgerätes in cm ca.	54 × 54	17 × 11 (ohne Schachbrett)	20 × 17
Batteriebetrieb ohne Zusatzgerät	nicht möglich	möglich	möglich
Zugeingaben durch	Sensoren	Tasten	Tasten
Anzeige der Computerzüge durch	Kennz. auf Schachbrett	Skala	Skala
Tonsignale beim Computerzug	vorhanden	vorhanden	nicht vorhanden
Begleittexte	nicht vorhanden	nicht vorhanden	geschrieben
Sonderzubehör lt. Hersteller	Tragetasche (148 DM), ab Herbst 81 Modul SIII (698 DM)	Tasche (15,50 DM), ab Herbst 81 neues Programm Mephisto X (250 DM), zusammen mit vollelektron. Schachbrett (800 DM)	12-V-Auto-Adapter (28 DM)
SPIELEIGENSCHAFTEN	gut	zufriedenstellend	mangelhaft
Beherrschung der Regeln	gut	+ mangelhaft	- mangelhaft
Farbwahl	sehr gut	++	sehr gut
Initiativtest	zufriedenstellend	o	mangelhaft
Eröffnungstest	gut	+	zufriedenstellend
Endspieletest	gut	+	gut
Rechentiefe	gut	+	gut
Turnierergebnis mit Stellungsbewertung (siehe Tabelle)	gut	+	zufriedenstellend
AUSSTATTUNG / BEDIENUNG	gut	gut	zufriedenstellend
Bedienungsanleitung	zufriedenstellend	o	zufriedenstellend
Eingabe der Züge	einfach	+	einfach
Eingabe von Stellungen	einfach	+	zufriedenstellend
Schachanzeige	vorhanden	+	vorhanden
Stellungskorrektur und Zugrücknahme	zufriedenstellend	o	zufriedenstellend
Spielstandskontrolle	einfach	+	zufriedenstellend
Eingabe von Sonderzügen	einfach	+	einfach
Übersichtlichkeit von Schachbrett und Schachfiguren	gut	+	Brett und Figuren nicht vorhanden
Lesbarkeit bei hellem Licht	schlecht	-	gut
Bedienung der Tasten	zufriedenstellend	o	gut
ELEKTRISCHE SICHERHEIT	zufriedenstellend	gut	mangelhaft
des Netzteils bei Verwendung mit Schachcomputer			Kriech- und Luftstrecken würden nicht eingehalten, Wärmebeständigkeit ist nicht gewährleistet.

¹⁾ Führt zur Abwertung
(siehe »Ausgewählt ...«, Seite 25)

²⁾ Im Lieferumfang Koffer enthalten.

³⁾ Lt. Hersteller inzwischen mit geändertem
Programm als Diplomat II

Fig.10: 1981 Comparison test, individual results (excerpt). Source: Stiftung Warentest (ed.): Test Schachcomputer. Fast alle mattgesetzt, in: test, volume 16, no. 8, August 1981, page 26

Kasparov's defeat in 1997

Modern chess-playing programs are so strong that even top players can hardly keep up, see Fig.11. The tide turned with the defeat of the then world chess champion Garry Kasparov against IBM's Deep Blue chess-playing computer in 1997. The game program Alphago from Google subsidiary Deepmind also came out on top.

Fig.11: 1996 Deep Blue vs. Kasparov match in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. Credit Laurence Kesterson, Corbis/Sygma, Computer History Museum, Mountain View, CA

This post is the fifth in a series that presents selected technical marvels from the fields of computing technology, mathematics, astronomy, surveying, time measurement, looms, and automatons (automaton figures, chess-playing machines, musical automatons, automaton writers, drawing automatons, automaton clocks, picture clocks, globes, and historical robots). The examples are largely from the 15th to 20th centuries and do not claim to be exhaustive. In particular, artifacts are included for which high-quality illustrations are available. Most of the objects come from Europe, with a few from Africa, America, Asia, and Australia. The order is predominantly chronological. Famous names such as Archimedes, Hipparchus, Heron of Alexandria, Leonardo da Vinci, Galileo Galilei, John Napier, Jost Bürgi, Blaise Pascal, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, and Charles Babbage are associated with these works. In some cases, however, the inventors are unknown (e.g. abacus, Antikythera Mechanism, yupana, quipu); see [Technical Marvels, Part 4: Leonardo da Vinci's Robots – Communications of the ACM](#)

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August 2024